

Report on suitability of spectroradiometers for scotopic and mesopic luminance – illuminance measurements

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SUMMARY

The photometric characteristics and performances of luminaires are specified given the emitted luminous flux, the luminous intensity distribution and the luminous efficacy. Some Standards require also other parameters, like the luminous flux emitted in peculiar solid angles (like the upward light output ratio R_{ULO}), but they can be deduced knowing the luminous intensity distribution.

Generally these quantities are measured considering photopic photometry. However, in many applications, like road lighting, the lighting level conditions are typical of the mesopic range. Traditionally, also in these cases photopic quantities are used to characterize performances of the lighting installation or to specify standard requirements.

With traditional lighting sources (i.e. sodium low and high pressure sodium lamps) this convention does not create any problems in road lighting applications, because the requirements are given considering experimental results and heuristics approximations both obtained using photopic units.

Considering LEDs or “white light” sources, as their emitted spectra is completely different from these of traditional sources, the use in Standards of mesopic units for specifying requirements at the lighting level adopted in road lighting installations could permits considerable energy savings.

In order to apply this mesopic concept, a given luminaire should be characterized considering the effective road lighting conditions. Indeed, the models of mesopic vision correlate the visibility function to the adaptation level of the eyes expressed as photopic luminance.

Therefore, a mesopic luminous intensity distribution of a luminaire cannot be measured directly if the adaptation level found in installations is not known. To obtain the mesopic characterization of a luminaire for a given adaptation level the spectral distribution of the observed light shall be known.

The proposed solution is to measure both the photopic luminous intensity distribution and the relative spectral distribution at each direction of emission. If appropriate algorithms are used, these two information permit to evaluate the mesopic quantities for any application conditions.

The proposed method has the advantage to obtain at the same time the photopic luminous intensity distribution, as required by current Standards, and, as ancillary data, the spectral distribution that can be used only if necessary.

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LIST OF SYMBOLS

c	number of C-planes.
C_l	the l^{th} plane C ($l = 1 \dots, c$) of the CIE C-planes system [8], in degree
C_γ	direction of emission of the light identified by plane C and angle γ on the systems of planes named C-planes, in degree.
$C_r \gamma_r$	the r^{th} direction of emission of the light identified by plane C_r (azimuthal angle) and the vertical photometric angle γ_r ($r = 1 \dots, d$) of the CIE C-planes system, in degree
$C_{jp} \gamma_{jp}$	the angular direction of the j^{th} vertex of the quadrilateral that identifies the p^{th} set of directions of emission ($j = 1, \dots, 4$).
d	number of the relative spectral distribution that shall be specified or of the emission directions considered.
e	number of the special colour rendering index R_i .
$f(\lambda)$	ratio between the reflected radiant flux $\Phi_r(\lambda)$ the lens captures and the reflected radiant flux $\Phi_r(\lambda)$ by the detector surface. Dimension 1.
f_r	normalizing factor for calculating the r^{th} reduced relative spectral distribution from the r^{th} relative spectral distribution.
g	number of vertical photometric angles γ .
DIR r	code to specify that the data of the r^{th} ($r = 1, \dots, d$) direction of emission are considered.
h	running number for identifying a wavelength.
i	running number for identifying the special colour rendering index R_i .
$I(C, \gamma)$	luminous intensity in the direction C_γ , in candelas.
$I_\lambda(C, \gamma, \lambda)$	spectral distribution of the radiant intensity in direction C_γ , in watt per steradian per nanometre.
j	running number for identifying a vertex of the quadrilateral that identifies a set of directions of emission.
$k(X)$	coverage factor of the quantity X . Dimension 1.
$k_{ang}(\lambda)$	factor to consider the influence of the angle of incidence of the light on the acceptance area of the detector. Dimension 1.
$k_{bwh}(\lambda)$	is a factor to consider the influence of the spectrometer bandwidth and other parameters of the spectrometer that may influence the output signal but are not specified by peculiar factor in the model. Dimension 1.
$k_{cal}(\lambda)$	calibration coefficient of the measurement system for the relative spectral distribution. Dimension inverse of count.
$k_{dim}(\lambda)$	factor to consider the influence of the dimension of the measured light source. Dimension 1.

$k_{int}(\lambda)$	factor to consider the influence of numerical interpolation or integration to obtain output values at the wavelength used in calibration or in the CIE $V(\lambda)$ tables. Dimension 1.
$k_{lin}(\lambda)$	factor to correct the non linearity of the spectrometer. Dimension 1.
$k_{lin,mea}(\lambda)$	factor to correct the non linear behaviour of the spectrometer at the signal level acquired during measurement of the light source. Dimension 1.
$k_{lin,sla}(\lambda)$	factor to correct the non linear behaviour of the spectrometer at the signal level acquired during measurement of the ambient stray light. Dimension 1.
$k_{lin,slf}(\lambda)$	factor to correct the non linear behaviour of the spectrometer at the signal level acquired during measurement of the instrument stray light. Dimension 1.
$k_{noi}(\lambda)$	factor to evaluate the influence of noise in the spectrometer output. Dimension 1.
$k_{noi,mea}(\lambda)$	factor to evaluate the influence of noise in the spectrometer output at signal level acquired during measurement of the light source. Dimension 1.
$k_{noi,sla}(\lambda)$	factor to evaluate the influence of noise in the spectrometer output at the signal level acquired during measurement of the ambient stray light. Dimension 1.
$k_{noi,slf}(\lambda)$	factor to evaluate the influence of noise in the spectrometer output at the signal level acquired during measurement of the instrument stray light. Dimension 1.
$k_{nor}(\lambda)$	normalize factor to obtain the maximum value of $S(\lambda)$ equal to 1. Dimension 1.
$k_{pol}(\lambda)$	factor to consider the influence of polarization of the measured light. Dimension 1.
$k_{uni}(\lambda)$	factor to consider the influence of irradiance uniformity on the acceptance area of the detector. Dimension 1.
$k_{sou}(\lambda)$	factor to consider the influence of the measured light source (instability, effect of the electrical conditions, ambient temperature and humidity influence, etc.). Dimension 1.
$K_l(C, \gamma)$	coefficient of proportionality for the luminous intensity, in watt per steradian per nanometre.
K_m	maximum value, in photopic vision conditions, of the luminous efficacy of a radiation, in lumen per watt.
I_r	value of the luminous intensity emitted in the r^{th} direction of emission, in candelas.
$I_{l,q}$	value of the luminous intensity for the l^{th} plane C and the q^{th} vertical photometric angle γ , in candelas.
l	running number for identifying a C plane.
m_r	number of set of emission directions for the r^{th} relative spectral distribution.
n	number of the first user-defined sections used for spectral data.
p	running number for identifying a set of directions of emission.
q	running number for identifying a vertical photometric angle γ of the CIE C-planes system [8].
r	running number for identifying a relative spectral distribution or a direction of emission.
$R_{a,r}$	value of the CIE 1974 general colour rendering index R_a for the r^{th} direction of emission. Dimension 1.
$R_{a,l,q}$	value of the CIE 1974 general colour rendering index R_a for the l^{th} plane C and the q^{th} vertical photometric angle γ . Dimension 1.

$R_{i,r}$	value of the i^{th} CIE 1974 special colour rendering index R_i for the r^{th} direction of emission ($i = 1, \dots, e$). Dimension 1.
$S(\lambda)$	measured relative spectral distribution of the incident radiation $\Phi(\lambda)$. Dimension 1.
$S_{cal}(\lambda)$	relative spectral distribution of the light source used for the calibration of the spectrometer. Dimension 1.
$s_c(\lambda)$	spectral responsivity of the detector cell in ampere per watt.
$s_d(\lambda)$	spectral responsivity of the detector in ampere per watt.
$S_{h,r}$	value of the r^{th} reduced relative spectral distribution at wavelength λ_h . Dimension 1.
$S_{h,r}$	value of the r^{th} relative spectral distribution at wavelength $\lambda_{h,r}$. Dimension 1.
$S_{h,l,q}$	value of the relative spectral distribution at λ_h for the l^{th} plane C and the q^{th} vertical photometric angle γ . Dimension 1.
$s_s(\lambda)$	spectral responsivity of spectrometer in count per watt.
st	numerical code to identify the structure of data in a user defined section.
str	numerical code to identify the structure of data of the user defined section $n + r$ used for specifying the r^{th} relative spectral distribution.
$T_{cp,r}$	value of correlated colour temperature T_{cp} for the r^{th} direction of emission, in kelvin.
$T_{cp,l,q}$	value of correlated colour temperature T_{cp} for the l^{th} plane C and the q^{th} vertical photometric angle γ , in kelvin.
$u(X)$	uncertainty or tolerance (according to the data described in the file) of the quantity X. The value specifies the semi-amplitude of the uncertainty or tolerance interval.
u_s	numerical code to specify if the uncertainty or tolerance are given in absolute values ($u_s = 1$) or in relative values ($u_s = 2$).
w	number of wavelength.
x_r	value of the CIE chromaticity coordinate x for the r^{th} direction of emission. Dimension 1.
$x_{l,q}$	value of the CIE chromaticity coordinate x for the l^{th} plane C and the q^{th} vertical photometric angle γ . Dimension 1.
$y_{l,q}$	value of the CIE chromaticity coordinate y for the l^{th} plane C and the q^{th} vertical photometric angle γ . Dimension 1.
y_r	value of the CIE chromaticity coordinate y for the r^{th} direction of emission. Dimension 1.
$Y_d(\lambda)$	output signal of the photometric detector at a given wavelength λ , in counts.
$Y_s(\lambda)$	output signal of the spectrometer for an observed radiation at a given wavelength λ , in counts.
$Y_{s,cal}(\lambda)$	output signal of the spectrometer during calibration for an observed radiation at a given wavelength λ , in counts.
$Y_{s,dark}(\lambda)$	output signal of the spectrometer at a given wavelength λ in the absence of observed radiation, in counts.
$Y_{s,mea}(\lambda)$	output signal of the spectrometer during measurement of the light source at a given wavelength λ , in counts.

$Y_{s,sl}(\lambda)$	output signal of the spectrometer at a given wavelength λ due to stray light due to reflections inside the instrument, in counts.
$Y_{s,sla}(\lambda)$	output signal of the spectrometer at a given wavelength λ due to stray light due to reflections in the ambient (lab), in counts.
Φ	luminous flux of the luminaire, in lumen.
$\Phi(\lambda)$	radiant flux incident on the detector surface, in watt.
$\Phi_r(\lambda)$	radiant flux reflected by the detector surface, in watt.
$\Phi_c(\lambda)$	radiant flux the lens of the spectrometer captures, in watt.
$\Phi_\lambda(\lambda)$	measured spectral distribution of the incident radiation, in watt per nanometre.
$\Delta\lambda$	the bandwidth of the spectrometer, in nanometre.
γ_q	the q^{th} vertical photometric angle γ ($q = 1 \dots, g$) of the CIE C-planes system [8], in degree.
λ_h	value of the h^{th} wavelength ($h = 1 \dots, w$), in nm.
$\lambda_{h,r}$	value of the h^{th} wavelength ($h = 1 \dots, w$) of the $S_{h,r}$ relative spectral distribution value, in nm.
λ_{max}	wavelength at which $\Phi_\lambda(\lambda)$ has its maximum value, in nanometre.
$\rho_g(\lambda)$	spectral reflectance of the detector opaline glass measured at normal incidence and at the spectrometer lens observation angle. Dimension 1.
$\tau(\lambda)$	spectral transmittance of the detector filter measured. Dimension 1.
$\tau_g(\lambda)$	spectral transmittance of the detector opaline glass. Dimension 1.
$\tau_s(\lambda)$	spectral transmittance of the lens of the spectrometer. Dimension 1.
$\tau_o(\lambda)$	spectral transmittance of the fibre optics of the spectrometer. Dimension 1.
ν	orientation angle of the luminaire, in degrees.
θ	tilt angle of the luminaire, in degrees.
ψ	rotation angle of the luminaire, in degrees.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENM	CEN modified file format
CENR	CEN radiometric modified file format
CIE	Commission Internationale de l'Eclairage
EMRP	European Metrology Research Programme
JRP	Joint Research Project

LED	Lighting Emitting Diode
NMI	National Measurement Institute
NSRD	Normalize spectral radiometric data
NWLH	Number of Wavelengths.
RSDD	Relative Spectral Distribution – Data.
RSDW	Relative Spectral Distribution – Wavelength.
S/P ratio	Scotopic Photopic Ratio
SSL	Solid State Lighting
ULOR	Upward Light Output Ratio
UNI	Ente Nazionale Italiano di Unificazione (Italian Standard Organization)

1 INTRODUCTION

The photometric characteristics and performances of luminaires are specified given the emitted luminous flux, the luminous intensity distribution and the luminous efficacy. Some standards require other parameters, like the luminous flux emitted in peculiar solid angles (e.g. the upward light output ratio R_{ULO}), but these can be gathered knowing the luminous intensity distribution.

Generally, these quantities are measured considering photopic photometry. In many applications, like road lighting, the lighting level conditions are typical of the mesopic range. Traditionally, also in these cases photopic quantities are used to characterize performances of the lighting installation or to specify standard requirements.

For road lighting applications, the use of mesopic quantities for given normative requirements could permit a important energy saving without reducing the road safety conditions.

CEN standards consider exclusively photopic quantities. The revision of the actual CEN standard started in 2010 but the first decision has been to maintain this approach also in the next standard, scheduled for the middle of 2013 [1]. The reasons of this choice are:

- the lack of experience in the use of mesopic quantities;
- the luminaires characterization does not give information to correctly calculate mesopic quantities;
- the absence of proposal for algorithms aimed at calculating road lighting installation using mesopic quantities.

For these reasons some national standards try to adopt simplified approaches partially following guidelines written in a draft CIE technical report [2]. For example the Italian standard for the selection of lighting classes requires a risk analysis to find the best ones for a given road situation. When this class is settled, if the peripheral vision is important and if the light sources have a colour rendering index Ra greater than 60, the designer can select the first class with less performance requirements.

The measurement system proposed in this report is an approach to solve the luminaire characterization problem, i.e. the second point mentioned before.

The current models of mesopic vision correlate the mesopic visibility function to the adaptation level of the eyes expressed as photopic luminance and to the spectral distribution of the observed light. The adaptation level changes according to applications and situations and of course could not be known when the luminaire is characterized in laboratory. For applying the mesopic concept, an exhaustive characterization of a luminaire requires the measurement of spectral distribution of the emitted light.

The solution to measure only the spectral radiant intensity distribution is possible, but not convenient because:

- for application in photopic range the luminous quantities shall be evaluated from spectral data, i.e. there is a surplus of data;

- all standards require the knowledge of the luminous intensity distribution in photonic units.

The proposed solution consists in measuring both the photopic luminous intensity distribution and the relative spectral distribution of the light in each measured direction. If appropriate algorithms are used, these two set of data permit to evaluate the mesopic quantities in applications.

The proposed method has the advantage to obtain at the same time the photopic luminous intensity distribution as required by actual standards and, as ancillary data, the spectral distribution that can be used only if necessary and if the calculation program is able to manage it. The method takes into account the great influence the luminaire optical systems can have on the emitted spectral distribution. For example, luminaires especially designed for road lighting applications, show great and important variations of the spectral distribution with the emission directions [5].

There are luminaires for which this variation is significantly high and others that have variations inside the measurement uncertainty. As the proposed method permits to know the spectral distribution for every measured direction, for exchanges of luminaire characteristics it could be possible to reduce the number of data considering symmetry or tolerances.

A file structure shall be defined for this purpose. Three different approaches are here considered.

The first one is a modification of the actual CEN standard file [6] that is compatible with the CIE file for interchanges of photometric data [7]. This solution generates a file compatible with the normative requirements that can be read by the current software, even if specific procedures are necessary to correctly interpret the new set of data.

The second one is an integration of the actual CEN standard file with specific field for the spectral data. The same approach used in defining field of the CEN standard is followed. This approach can be considered as a pre-normative guide for future improvements of the CEN file.

The CEN file system originates from a CIE report dated 1995 [7] that describes an information technology (IT) older than 20 years. Currently more interesting and flexible file structures could be defined using for example the Extensible Markup Language (XML) that defines a set of rules for encoding data in a format that is both human and machine readable. A XML Structure is the third possible approach. The definition of a standard and complete xml structure for the exchange of luminaires data is out of the scope of this report but a proposal of a structure for the data mainly important in this application is described.

2 THE SPECTRORADIOMETRIC MEASUREMENT SYSTEM

2.1 Measurement methods

The spectroradiometric measurement system has been designed to be installed at the INRIM goniophotometer for the characterization of light sources and luminaires.

The INRIM goniophotometer is a type 4 instrument [6] adopting the C-plane coordinate system. The photometric head is moved on a virtual sphere with a radius of $(2\,793 \pm 0,1)$ mm. At the centre of the sphere the light source photometric centre can be located with an uncertainty of ± 1 mm using two aligned laser beams. The same beams permit the definition of the second and third axes with an uncertainty of $0,1^\circ$. The first axis is defined considering the encoder of the vertical photometric angle at the 0° and 90° positions. The resolution of this encoder is of $0,01^\circ$ and therefore also the first axis is defined with an uncertainty of $0,1^\circ$.

The detector can be moved in spherical zones (parallel to the equator) or in spherical segments (from pole to pole). This movement is generally adopted for luminaires. For mechanical reasons the maximum vertical photometric angle measurable is 175° . During the measurement the detector moves continuously at different angular speeds. The acquisition of the photocurrent can be done at fixed angles (generally with C planes steps of 5° and vertical photometric angle γ steps of 1°) or at variable angles the maximum speed permitted by the acquisition system of the photocurrent.

The goniophotometer has two detectors:

- A silicon cell with an picoammeter, working as an illuminance meter, for the luminous flux measurement and the luminous intensity distribution of luminaires of small dimensions;
- An ILMD for the measurement of luminaires of greater dimensions using the near field techniques

The first detector is calibrated for illuminance measurement and the light source luminous flux is obtained from its readings through a numerical integration algorithm, while the luminous intensity distribution is calculated using the inverse-square law. This detector is the reference device for flux measurements

The images acquired by the ILMD detector are elaborate though an ad hoc algorithms to obtain the luminance distribution of the luminaires. The method is calibrated using the illuminance readings. This detector requires a metrological characterization of many parameters (like linearity, stray light and ghost imagines, pixel relative sensitivity, etc.) but not an absolute calibration in SI units. For every angular position the measured luminance with the ILMD shall produce the same measured illuminance by the illuminance meter.

The described system measures the spectral distribution of the light source and the illuminance on the virtual sphere surface. The acquire spectral data permits to increase the accuracy of the illuminance measurement correcting the spectral mismatching of the illuminance meter responsivity respect to the $V(\lambda)$ and gives the

relative spectral distribution of the radiation.

2.1 Measurement principle

A schema of the measurement system to illustrate the measurement principle is showed in Figure 1.

The light source lights the detector of the calibrated illuminance meter. The lighted surface of the detector reflects a fraction of this light that is captured by a lens and measured by a spectrometer, connected through a fibre optics.

The system is realized using an aluminium tube with two baffles to reduce the influence of the lab stray light and inter-reflections between internal tube wall and the detector. The lens focuses the detector surface on the fibre optics input. At its output a CCD array spectrometer acquires the spectral signal. The readings of the two detectors are synchronized with the same integration time: this assures to measure the radiation in the same direction of emission, also if the detector is rotating during the measurement.

Figure 1 A schema of the measurement system. The length and the diameter of the tube are evaluated considering the measurement distance and the maximum dimension of the source.

The dimension of the tube and the diameter of the two baffles are designed to reduce the stray light influence. The position of the baffles can be changed according to the source maximum dimension.

The path of the optical radiation is show in Figure 2. If $\Phi(\lambda)$ is the radiant flux incident on the detector surface, the spectrometer lens capture a fraction of the reflected flux $\Phi_r(\lambda)$:

$$\Phi_c(\lambda) = f(\lambda) \Phi_r(\lambda) = f(\lambda) \Phi(\lambda) \rho_g(\lambda)$$

where:

- $\Phi(\lambda)$ is the radiant flux incident on the detector surface, in watt.
- $\Phi_r(\lambda)$ is the radiant flux reflected by the detector surface, in watt.
- $\Phi_c(\lambda)$ is the radiant flux the lens of the spectrometer captures, in watt.

$f(\lambda)$ is the ratio between the reflected radiant flux $\Phi_c(\lambda)$ the lens captures and the reflected radiant flux $\Phi_r(\lambda)$. Dimension 1.

$\rho_g(\lambda)$ is the spectral reflectance of the detector opaline glass measured at normal incidence and at the spectrometer lens observation angle. Dimension 1.

The output signal $Y_s(\lambda)$ of the spectrometer, in counts and for an observed radiation of a given wavelength λ , is:

$$Y_s(\lambda) = \Phi_c(\lambda) \tau_s(\lambda) \tau_o(\lambda) s_s(\lambda)$$

where:

$\Phi_c(\lambda)$ is the radiant flux the lens of the spectrometer captures, in watt.

$\Phi_r(\lambda)$ is the radiant flux reflected by the detector surface, in watt.

$\tau_s(\lambda)$ is the spectral transmittance of the lens of the spectrometer. Dimension 1.

$\tau_o(\lambda)$ is the spectral transmittance of the fibre optics of the spectrometer. Dimension 1.

$s_s(\lambda)$ is the spectral responsivity of the spectrometer in count per watt.

Considering the bandwidth $\Delta\lambda$ of the spectrometer, the measured spectral distribution of the incident radiation $\Phi_\lambda(\lambda)$ is:

$$\Phi_\lambda(\lambda) = \frac{\int_{\Delta\lambda} \frac{\Phi(\lambda)}{d\lambda} d\lambda}{\Delta\lambda}$$

If λ_{max} is the wavelength at which $\Phi_\lambda(\lambda)$ has its maximum value, the relative spectral distribution $S(\lambda)$ of the incident radiation $\Phi(\lambda)$ is:

$$S(\lambda) = \frac{\Phi_\lambda(\lambda)}{\Phi_\lambda(\lambda_{max})} = \frac{Y_s(\lambda)}{\tau_s(\lambda) \tau_o(\lambda) s_s(\lambda) f(\lambda) \rho_g(\lambda)} \frac{\tau_s(\lambda_{max}) \tau_o(\lambda_{max}) s_s(\lambda_{max}) f(\lambda_{max}) \rho_g(\lambda_{max})}{Y_s(\lambda_{max})}$$

The output signal $Y_d(\lambda)$ of the photometric detector, in ampere and for a monochromatic radiation of a given wavelength λ , is:

$$Y_d(\lambda) = \Phi(\lambda) \tau_g(\lambda) \tau_f(\lambda) s_c(\lambda) = \Phi(\lambda) s_d(\lambda)$$

where:

$\Phi(\lambda)$ is the radiant flux incident on the detector surface, in watt.

$\tau_g(\lambda)$ is the spectral transmittance of the detector opaline glass. Dimension 1.

$\tau_f(\lambda)$ is the spectral transmittance of the detector filter measured. Dimension 1.

$s_c(\lambda)$ is the spectral responsivity of the detector cell, in ampere per watt.

$s_d(\lambda)$ is the spectral responsivity of the all detector, in ampere per watt:

$$s_d(\lambda) = \tau_g(\lambda) \tau_f(\lambda) s_c(\lambda)$$

The spectral transmittances of the opaline glass and of the filter shall be considered the light distribution on their surface and the direction of incidence of the light. These aspects are considered in the measurement uncertainty evaluation.

The illuminance meter reads the value E_r , it can be written as:

$$E_r = k_{cal} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{Y_d(\lambda)}{d\lambda} d\lambda$$

where:

k_{cal} is a convenient calibration coefficient, in lux per ampere.

According to the procedure for the measurement uncertainty evaluations [4], to obtain the illuminance value this result shall be considered as an input quantity in the functional relationship that link the illuminance (output quantity) to a set of influence parameters (input quantities).

An important input quantity is a correction factor to compensate the mismatch between the illuminance meter spectral responsivity $s_d(\lambda)$ and the spectral luminous efficiency $V(\lambda)$. If the relative spectral distribution $S(\lambda)$ of the incident radiation $\Phi(\lambda)$ is known, the reading of the illuminance meter can be corrected by multiplying this value by the spectral mismatch correction factor F_{TC} :

$$F_{TC} = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda) V(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int_0^{\infty} S_r(\lambda) V(\lambda) d\lambda} \frac{\int_0^{\infty} S_r(\lambda) s_{r,d}(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda) s_{r,d}(\lambda) d\lambda}$$

where:

$V(\lambda)$ is the spectral luminous efficiency $V(\lambda)$. Dimension 1.

$S_r(\lambda)$ is the relative spectral distribution of the light source used during calibration (reference source). Dimension 1.

$s_{r,d}(\lambda)$ is the relative spectral responsivity of the detector. Dimension 1:

$$s_{r,d} = \frac{s_d(\lambda)}{s_d(\lambda_{max})}$$

λ_{max} is the wavelength at which $s_d(\lambda)$ has its maximum value. Dimension nanometre.

Generally, the luminous intensity distribution is the parameter standards require for the photometric characterization of luminaires. If the luminous intensity and the relative spectral distribution of the radiation emitted in the direction $C \gamma$ of the systems of planes named C-planes [6] are known, the spectral distribution of the radiant intensity in the same direction can be obtained as:

$$I_{\lambda}(C, \gamma, \lambda) = K_I(C, \gamma) S(C, \gamma, \lambda)$$

$$K_I(C, \gamma) = \frac{I(C, \gamma)}{K_m \int_0^{\infty} S(C, \gamma, \lambda) V(\lambda) d\lambda}$$

where:

$I_{\lambda}(C, \gamma, \lambda)$ is the spectral distribution of the radiant intensity in direction $C \gamma$, in watt per steradian per nanometre.

$K_I(C, \gamma)$ is a coefficient of proportionality, in watt per steradian per nanometre.

K_m is the maximum value, in photopic vision conditions, of the luminous efficacy of a radiation, in lumen per watt.

$S(C, \gamma, \lambda)$ is the relative spectral distribution of the radiation in direction $C \gamma$. Dimension 1.

$I(C, \gamma)$ is the luminous intensity in the direction $C \gamma$ in candelas.

Figure 2 The paths of the optical radiation.

2.2 The INRIM instrument

In Figure 3 the mechanical parts of the measurement system are shown mounted on the INRIM goniophotometer.

The illuminance detector is a LMT photometer head AP 30 SCT with a very fine $V(\lambda)$ approximation ($f_1 < 1\%$) calibrated using an illuminant A source. The reflectance of the opaline glass was measured considering an angle of incidence of 0° and a reflection angle of 30° corresponding to the mechanical layout of the optical system. The measurement has been carried out considering the opaline glass alone or installed in the detector (Figure 4). The difference between the two conditions is quite high (Figure 5): the ratio of the two functions has a maximum value of about 1,49 near 640 nm but the most important effect is its variability with wavelength (about 4%) that highlights the importance to have a description of the influence of internal reflections in the detector. The radiant flux reflected by the detector filter that reaches the incidence half-space and is captured by the spectrometer lens is an important fraction of the measured light. The correct evaluation of this fraction is difficult because it depends mainly from:

- the uniformity of the illuminance on the detector acceptance surface,
- the rotation, respect to the vertical axis of the measurement system, of the detector,
- the direction of the incidence of the light.

Considering the radius of the INRIM goniophotometer, the dimension of the detector and the maximum dimension of luminaires (1,5 m):

- The uniformity of the illuminance on the detector acceptance surface is usually very high, except at angles near cut-off, where greater uncertainty could be acceptable.
- The maximum angle of incidence respect to the normal of the detector surface is 15° . Luminaires of big dimensions with great disuniformity between left, right or central parts of their luminous surface are not common, therefore the luminous flux can be considered uniform, in the visual angle the detector sees the luminaire. The influence of the increment of this angle with the increment of the luminaire dimension is considered in the measurement uncertainty evaluation.
- For its calibration, the detector is removed from the measurement system and the repeatability of its angular positioning in its holder is lower than 5° . The influence of this rotation can be reduced during the calibration of the spectral part of the device and it is considered in the measurement uncertainty evaluation.

The detector filter adopts the partial filtering concept and the measurement of its reflectance cannot be done with adequate measurement uncertainty. Even though a complete model of the influence of the filter reflectance is not possible, the knowledge of the opaline glass transmittance can give information for a correct measurement uncertainty evaluation and improved metrological characterization method of the instrument. The opaline glass transmittance obtained in 30/d geometry (an approximation of the real geometry condition of the detector but with the inversion of the incidence and observation conditions) is shown in Figure 6.

The part of the instrument used for the spectral measurement is composed by:

- A lens that sees the acceptance area of the detector at a 30° angle respect to the surface normal;
- A fibre optics, 1 m long;
- An Ocean Optics CCD spectrometer model USB2000 with a grating working from 350 nm to 850 nm and a resolution of 1,4 nm.

The focal length of the lens has been selected to create an image of the detector surface at the fibre optics input. To improve the quality of this image and to maximize framed acceptance areas of the detector avoiding to frame part of the detector holder, the acceptance surface plane, the lens plane and the image plane (i.e. the plane of the input surface of the fibre optics) are inclined with angles that are a compromise between the Scheimpflug condition, the minimization of perspective distortion and mechanical constrains. This inclination is not shown in the schematic draw of Figure 1.

The lens has a diameter of 30 mm and an aperture angle of about 12° respect to the centre of the detector surface.

The measurement uncertainty of the INRIM instrument depends also from the luminaire characteristics but is generally better than 1 %.

Figure 3 The measurement system installed on the INRIM goniophotometer. The two other detector holders are partially visible, while the two baffles are removed for clearness.

Figure 4 The spectral reflectance of the opaline glass in the direction of observation of the spectrometer and with normal incidence.

Figure 5 Ratio of the spectral transmittance of the opaline glass when measured mounted in the detector and alone.

Figure 6 The spectral transmittance of the opaline glass.

2.3 Calibration

The instrument was design for the characterization of luminaires and for the correction of the detector reading due to its spectral responsivity mismatch respect to the $V(\lambda)$ function. In both situations the required uncertainty should be compatible with measurement procedures typical for luminaire characterization and testing lab aims, while for NMI most stringent applications, an improved calibration techniques and uncertainty evaluation model should be developed if need.

The following description considers the typical situation of a testing laboratory and follows with some minor simplification the procedure adopted at INRIM. The metrological characterization of the measurement system to obtain parameters for the measurement uncertainty budget is described in §2.4.

The calibration of the photometric detector is extremely important in the uncertainty budget and is carried out on the detector alone eventually with the same electronic equipment used for reading the detector photocurrent.

The calibration of the spectro-radiometric part is more complex. For the spectral responsivity there are two calibration possibilities:

- The calibration of the spectrometer and of the fibre optics using standard lamp (tungsten halogen light or LED fibre-coupled sources) and the measurement of the spectral reflectance of the acceptance surface of the detector and spectral transmittance of the lens
- The calibration of the entire system, using a small LED or incandescent calibrated lamp. In this case the

calibrated light source can be mounted at the centre of the goniophotometer simulating a real measurement situation.

The second solution is the most interesting because gives lowest measurement uncertainty. If a LED light source is used, the presence of a peak in the emitted spectra can also used to verify the wavelength calibration of the spectrometer. At the same time high power white LED sources has higher level of radiant flux in the blue range compared to incandescent or halogen lamps and this improve the signal to noise ratio in this region.

In the following the same wavelengths are used in the calibration certificate and in the measurement system. Interpolation or integration of the certificate data and/or of the measurement data could be done to obtain this condition.

If $S_{cal}(\lambda)$ is the relative spectral distribution of the calibration source given in the calibration certificate, the following equation can be used for calculate the calibration coefficient $k_{cal}(\lambda)$:

$$S_{cal}(\lambda) = k_{cal}(\lambda) k_{lin}(\lambda) \left(Y_{s,cal}(\lambda) - Y_{s,dark}(\lambda) \right)$$

where:

$k_{cal}(\lambda)$ is the calibration coefficient of the measurement system for the relative spectral distribution. Dimension inverse of count.

$k_{lin}(\lambda)$ is a factor to correct the non linearity of the spectrometer. Dimension 1.

$Y_{s,cal}(\lambda)$ is the output signal of the spectrometer during calibration for an observed radiation at a given wavelength λ , in counts.

$Y_{s,dark}(\lambda)$ is the output signal of the spectrometer at a given wavelength λ in the absence of observed radiation, in counts.

The evaluation of $k_{lin}(\lambda)$ is conventional: $k_{lin}(\lambda)$ can be equal to 1 at the calibration conditions or the calibration coefficient can the calculated as an average value at different irradiance values on the acceptance surface of the photometric detector. These values can be obtained changing the distance between the calibration source and the detector. The consequences of these approaches are considered during the measurement uncertainty evaluation.

The wavelength calibration of the spectrometer is independent from the optical system of the instrument and can be carried out using a mercury argon calibration source with fibre optics connector.

2.4 Measurement uncertainty evaluation

In the new measurement system the measurement uncertainty evaluation for the luminous intensity doesn't change respect to the classical method. Variation in the value of the parameter that evaluates the influence of the instrument stray light is the only difference. The instrument has the same form and dimension of the

shield used to reduce the effect of ambient stray light, the only difference is the presence of the lens that is not lighted directly.

The mathematical model adopted to describe the spectral measurement is:

$$S(\lambda) = \frac{1}{k_{nor}} k_{cal}(\lambda) k_{int}(\lambda) k_{bwh}(\lambda) k_{uni}(\lambda) k_{ang}(\lambda) k_{dim}(\lambda) k_{pol}(\lambda) k_{sou}(\lambda) \left(Y_{s,mea}(\lambda) k_{lin,mea}(\lambda) k_{noi,mea}(\lambda) - Y_{s,dark}(\lambda) k_{noi,dark}(\lambda) - Y_{s,sl i}(\lambda) k_{lin,sl i}(\lambda) k_{noi,sl i}(\lambda) - Y_{s,sla}(\lambda) k_{lin,sla}(\lambda) k_{noi,sla}(\lambda) \right)$$

where:

- $S(\lambda)$ is the measured relative spectral distribution of the incident radiation $\Phi(\lambda)$. Dimension 1.
- $k_{nor}(\lambda)$ is the normalize factor to obtain the maximum value of $S(\lambda)$ equal to 1. Dimension 1.
- $k_{cal}(\lambda)$ is the calibration coefficient of the measurement system for the relative spectral distribution. Dimension inverse of count.
- $k_{int}(\lambda)$ is a factor to consider the influence of numerical interpolation or integration to obtain output values at the wavelength used in calibration or in the CIE $V(\lambda)$ tables. Dimension 1.
- $k_{bwh}(\lambda)$ is a factor to consider the influence of the spectrometer bandwidth and other parameters of the spectrometer that may influence the output signal but are not specified by peculiar factor in the model. Dimension 1.
- $k_{uni}(\lambda)$ is a factor to consider the influence of irradiance uniformity on the acceptance area of the detector. Dimension 1.
- $k_{ang}(\lambda)$ is a factor to consider the influence of the angle of incidence of the light on the acceptance area of the detector. Dimension 1.
- $k_{dim}(\lambda)$ is a factor to consider the influence of the dimension of the measured light source. Dimension 1.
- $k_{pol}(\lambda)$ is a factor to consider the influence of polarization of the measured light. Dimension 1.
- $k_{sou}(\lambda)$ is a factor to consider the influence of the measured light source (instability, effect of the electrical conditions, ambient temperature and humidity influence, etc.). Dimension 1.
- $Y_{s,mea}(\lambda)$ is output signal of the spectrometer during measurement of the light source at a given wavelength λ , in counts.
- $k_{lin,mea}(\lambda)$ is a factor to correct the non linear behaviour of the spectrometer at the signal level acquired during measurement of the light source. Dimension 1.
- $k_{noi,mea}(\lambda)$ is a factor to evaluate the influence of noise in the spectrometer output at the signal level acquired during measurement of the light source. Dimension 1.
- $Y_{s,dark}(\lambda)$ is the output signal of the spectrometer at a given wavelength λ in the absence of observed radiation, in counts.

- $k_{noi,dark}(\lambda)$ is a factor to evaluate the influence of noise in the spectrometer output at the signal level acquired during measurement in dark condition. Dimension 1.
- $Y_{s,slf}(\lambda)$ is the output signal of the spectrometer at a given wavelength λ due to stray light due to reflections inside the instrument, in counts.
- $k_{lin,slf}(\lambda)$ is a factor to correct the non linear behaviour of the spectrometer at the signal level acquired during measurement of the instrument stray light. Dimension 1.
- $k_{noi,slf}(\lambda)$ is a factor to evaluate the influence of noise in the spectrometer output at the signal level acquired during measurement of the instrument stray light. Dimension 1.
- $Y_{s,sla}(\lambda)$ is the output signal of the spectrometer at a given wavelength λ due to stray light due to reflections in the ambient (lab), in counts.
- $k_{lin,sla}(\lambda)$ is a factor to correct the non linear behaviour of the spectrometer at the signal level acquired during measurement of the ambient stray light. Dimension 1.
- $k_{noi,sla}(\lambda)$ is a factor to evaluate the influence of noise in the spectrometer output at the signal level acquired during measurement of the ambient stray light. Dimension 1.

Every parameter in the formula has its own uncertainty value $u(X)$ where X is the parameter.

$k_{int}(\lambda)$ is evaluated considering the shape of the measure relative spectral distribution and the approximation of the algorithms used for interpolation (when the wavelength step of the spectrometer is larger than the step adopted in the calibration certificate) or integration (when the wavelength resolution of the spectrometer is greater than the step adopted in the calibration certificate).

$k_{bwh}(\lambda)$ is evaluated considering the influence of the spectrometer bandwidth or of other parameters not explicitly considered with peculiar factors (i.e. spectrometer stray light, influence of the wavelength calibration, influence of second and third order light, etc.).

$k_{uni}(\lambda)$ considers the influence of disuniformity of irradiance on the acceptance surface of the detector. The characterization can be done measuring the relative spectral distribution with different masking conditions of the light source

$k_{ang}(\lambda)$ considers the influence of disuniformity of radiance light source luminous surface. The parameter can be evaluated comparing the variation of the measured relative spectral distribution of a small source with the instrument turned across its vertical axis. Generally the influence of this parameter is very small and can be included in $k_{dim}(\lambda)$.

$K_{dim}(\lambda)$ considers the influence of the dimension of the light source luminous surface (i.e. the range of incident angles respect to the normal of detector surface). The parameter can be evaluated comparing the variation of the measured relative spectral distribution of the same source at different distances source – detector.

$K_{dim}(\lambda)$ considers the influence of polarized light. Differences in the measured relative spectral distribution

can be measured following the experimental set-up described in [6].

$K_{sou}(\lambda)$ considers the instability of the light source during measurement or correction factors need to compensate the effects of the electrical conditions, ambient temperature and humidity influence. It can be evaluated with measurement with the instrument in static conditions or from previous characterization of the light source.

$Y_{s,mea}(\lambda)$ is the output signal of the spectrometer during measurement of the light source at a given wavelength λ and for a given direction $C \gamma$. Generally only one measure is taken for every direction and the influence of noise shall be evaluated with ad hoc measurements in the characterization phase of the spectrometer or using the manufacture specifications. This aspect is considered by $k_{noi, mea}(\lambda)$.

$Y_{s,dark}(\lambda)$ is the output signal of the spectrometer in dark conditions. If several measures are taken before starting the real measurement the effect of spectrometer noise is evaluated using the dispersion of this data. In this case $k_{noi, dark}(\lambda)$ is not considered. The amplifier range and the integration time shall be the same of these used during the real measurement.

$Y_{s,slf}(\lambda)$ is the output signal due to stray light inside the instrument. The influence of stray light is generally negligible. A simple approximation of this value can be obtain removing the detector, but a more accurate solution requires a small elliptical shield to block out the light the detector reflect forward the lens. This parameter $k_{lin, slf}(\lambda)$ and $k_{noi, slf}(\lambda)$ are obtain, for a given source dimension, during the characterization phase of the instrument.

$Y_{s,sla}(\lambda)$ is the output signal due to stray light of the environment. For spectral measurement the influence of ambient stray light is generally negligible because due to reflection from black walls that practically doesn't modified the spectral distribution of the incident light. A fine approximation of this value can be obtained using a circular shield to block out the light from source to detector. For a given luminaire $Y_{s,sla}(\lambda)$ is obtained from this measurement or estimated using previously estimation. $k_{lin, slf}(\lambda)$ and $k_{noi, slf}(\lambda)$ are estimated or measured considering the amplifier range and the integration time used during the stray light measurement.

Generally in the $C \gamma$ directions useful for lighting applications, $Y_{s,dark}(\lambda)$, $Y_{s,slf}(\lambda)$ and $Y_{s,sla}(\lambda)$ are very low compared to $Y_{s,mea}(\lambda)$. Linearity corrections and noise estimation are not required because they don't influence significantly the measurement results. The formula can be simplify as:

$$S(\lambda) = \frac{1}{k_{nor}} k_{cal}(\lambda) k_{lin}(\lambda) k_{noi}(\lambda) k_{int}(\lambda) k_{bwh}(\lambda) k_{uni}(\lambda) k_{ang}(\lambda) k_{dim}(\lambda) k_{pol}(\lambda) k_{sou}(\lambda) \left(Y_{s,mea}(\lambda) - Y_{s,dark}(\lambda) - Y_{s,slf}(\lambda) - Y_{s,sla}(\lambda) \right)$$

$k_{lin}(\lambda)$ and $k_{noi}(\lambda)$ could be equal to 1 and $u(k_{lin})$ and $u(k_{noi})$ evaluated from the spectrometer specifications.

1. EXAMPLE OF MEASUREMENT RESULTS

Some measurement results carried out using the proposed system are shown.

The tested luminaire is a typical LED source used in Italy for highway tunnel lighting in the internal zone of the tunnel. In this situation the Italian standards [3][11] require a road luminance level of $2,25 \text{ cd m}^{-2}$ if the mesopic vision concept is applied. This can be adopted if the colour rendering index R_a of the used luminaires is greater than 60. Now and at the time the standards were developed, the S/P-ratio [2] was not used for specifying luminaire characteristics while the colour rendering index is normally declared by manufacturers. This approach represents a good approximation if the correlated colour temperature of the source is greater than about 5 kK and this is generally true in road lighting luminaires.

The tested luminaire has 36 LED each one equipped with a small lens to obtain the required luminous intensity distribution. The luminaire has a nominal luminous flux of 5 000 lm at 72 W of active power consume. The LED used has a nominal correlate colour temperature $T_{cp} = 6\ 000 \text{ K}$. This value was confirmed by measurements [5] where the results were $T_{cp} = (5\ 900 \pm 150) \text{ K}$.

The measures of the relative spectral distributions are shown in Figure 7 while the differences respect to the direction C180 - $\gamma 60$ are in Figure 8. As an example only some results at different γ angles are given for directions in the C180 plane: the energy in the green part of the spectra increases with the vertical photometric angle. At $\gamma = 60^\circ$ the effect of the detector noise becomes evident in the red region. This is not a real problem because this luminaire, designed for tunnel lighting, has a luminous intensity, in this C plane and for γ angle greater than 60° , lower than two orders of magnitude respect to the direction of maximum luminous intensity. In a real installation the light in these directions goes on wall surfaces where there aren't standard requirements.

A set of measured chromaticity coordinates at different C planes and vertical photometric angles is given in Figure 9.

In Figure 10 values of the S/P ratio are given for different directions. At the highest vertical photometric angles, the most important in road lighting if requirements are given as road surface luminance, the S/P ratio is about 7 % lower than at direction $\gamma = 0^\circ$.

Relative spectral distribution at the given directions of emission

Figure 7 The relative spectral distribution of the tested luminaire at different vertical photometric angles in the C0 – C180 plane.

Difference between the relative spectral distribution at a given direction of emission and the relative spectral distribution at the direction C180 - γ_0

Figure 8 Difference between the relative spectral distribution of the tested luminaire at a given vertical photometric angle and the relative spectral distribution at the polar direction $\gamma = 0^\circ$.

Figure 9 Calculated colour chromaticity coordinates for C planes 0, 90, 180, 270 and vertical photometric angles γ from 0° to 60° (10° step).

Figure 10

Calculated S/P ratio at different emission directions. Directions from 1 to 7 are in the C0 plane, 8 to 15 in C90, 16 to 23 in C180, 24 to 32 in C270. In every C plane vertical photometric angles γ start from 0° and have 10° step.

3 PROPOSED FILE FORMATS FOR DATA TRANSFER

3.1 CEN file format

The CEN file format for electronic data transfer is defined in EN 13032 part 1 [6] and it is a slightly modified version of the international file format described in CIE 102:1993 [7]. This means a reader designed for the CEN format could also read the CIE format file but not always vice versa is true.

There are also other industrial file formats that actually are very diffused and represent *de facto* standards. These formats are not considered here because often their formal description is not public or not known with the required details. In any case, the great majority of calculation softwares are able to read the CEN format and manufactures give their luminaires data also using this file format.

The CEN file format consists of two sections.

The first section consists of two parts:

- part 1 contains general information about the luminaire;
- part 2 contains specific information concerning the physical properties of the luminaire.

The second section can be appended to the file containing the first section, or it can be provided as a separate file. It consists of three parts:

- part 1 contains general information;
- part 2 includes a set of specific data concerning the measurement conditions;
- part 3 includes the luminous intensity distribution data.

The file is composed of two different line types:

- Structured lines: lines beginning with a specific code name. They can be of two types: key lines (which shall be included) or information lines (which can be left out).
- Unstructured lines: label lines and data lines.

After structured lines starting with CENF=, CENA= and PHOT=INCLUDE there may be a group of label lines which are unstructured and can carry any information.

A structured line gives information with the peculiar meaning specified by the code name. They are necessary to correctly characterize the luminaire performance.

The file format was originally developed for the exchange of photometric measurement results and in the mean time for been directly readable by humans too. The structure of the file is complete for describing a measurement result concerning the luminous flux and the luminous intensity distribution of a given luminaire. In this case the only metrological problem is the impossibility to declare the measurement uncertainty using structured lines.

The file is often used by manufacturers for distributing the photometric characteristics of a given product: the

results written in the file can be interpreted as performances of a product, like nominal values or best performance values or in other conditions according to what the manufacturer declares.

The file was also structured considering relative measurements of the luminous intensity distribution, i.e. photometric measurement in SI units relative to a specified bare lamp flux. The data considered in the file are the photometric data of luminaire relative to a total theoretical luminous flux of 1 000 lm of the luminaire lamps, when these are operated outside the luminaire and under reference conditions but with the same ballast(s) of the luminaire.

This was the typical solution adopted for the characterization of luminaires with traditional light sources. The idea was that when lamps of different luminous fluxes are installed in the same luminaires, its relative light distribution doesn't significantly change.

For LED sources, the European standards in development [8] or national ones [9] consider measurement in absolute unit. This requirement is not a problem using the CEN file because an optional information structured line (code LUBA= or LUmen BAis of photometry) specifies the base used for normalizing the luminous intensity values. A negative value (e.g. -1) indicates that intensities are in candelas, i.e. in absolute values.

The file is not useful to communicate spectral or colorimetric characteristic of luminaires because at the time of its development these parameters were:

- not considered with the importance currently given;
- not useful in computer programme for calculation of lighting installations.

The last reason is partially true also nowadays.

Colorimetric reference values (i.e. the nominal chromaticity coordinates x and y , the correlated colour temperature T_{cp} and the colour rendering index R) could be written as a description of the luminaire using optional information structured lines (TXTS= or TeXT Short = TeXT for a Short description of the luminaire and TXTF= or TeXT Full = TeXT for a Full description of the luminaire).

The file structure shall be modified or improved if the relative spectral distribution of the luminaire at different measurement directions is of interest, as for the LED luminaires.

3.2 The CEN file format modification

The file format does not provide lines to write spectral data, but it considers 10 user defined sections, where each section can have a maximum of 60 lines and each line can be a maximum of 78 characters in length.

These lines are not enough to give a complete description of the luminaire relative spectral distribution for every measured direction; rather they can be used to give some approximate information.

Considering these limitations, two different solutions are possible according to the luminaire characteristics

or the details of information needed.

In the same file both solutions can be used. They are identified by the st parameter.

In the first case ($st = 1$) the relative spectral distribution is given for a single direction of emission. Using all “user defined sections” a maximum of 9 directions can be specified.

In the second case ($st = 2$) a reduced set of relative spectral distribution can be given but each distribution has an angular range of validity. The set of angular directions are all the directions of emission inside a quadrilateral as show in Figure 11. This approach requires the specification of a range of variability of the spectral data at each wavelength. This data is not a measurement uncertainty but it defines an interval were, for each direction measured inside the specified angular range, the value of the relative spectral distribution lies, including also the measurement uncertainty values.

To specify this new structure the same convention used in the original file standard can be adopted. They are:

*Each line marked with a double asterisk “**” is a key line and shall be included in the file even if it does not provide data. Each line marked with a single asterisk “*” or a double asterisk “**” shall begin a new line. Descriptions enclosed within the “<” and “>” refer to the actual data stored on that line. All data is stored in the format of ISO Alphabet 5.*

Several “<” and “>” in the same line means that data with different meaning are given.

With these conventions, the spectral data are in the user-defined sections. If the first section used for spectral data has the number n ($n = 0, \dots, 8$), the number of consecutive sections needed are $d + 1$ (the maximum value of d will be $n - 9$) where d is the number of the relative spectral distribution that shall be specified. The proposed structure is the following:

* $USR_n=RSDW$ < user free field n specifying the wavelengths of the relative spectral distribution >

* < w >

* < $\lambda_1 \lambda_2 \dots \lambda_h \dots \lambda_w$ >

* $ENDU=$

* $USR_{n+1}=RSDD$ < user free field $n + 1$ specifying the first ($r = 1$) relative spectral distribution. Example of structure $st_r = 1$: data at a given direction >

* < st_r > < f_r > < $C_r \gamma_r$ >

* < $S_{1,r} S_{2,r} \dots S_{h,r} \dots S_{w,r}$ >

* $ENDU=$

* $USR_{n+2}=RSDD$ < user free field $n + 2$ specifying the second ($r = 2$) relative spectral distribution.

Example of structure $st_r = 2$: data considering a set of directions >

* < st_r > < f_r > < m_r >

* < [$C_{1,1}\gamma_{1,1}$ $C_{2,1}\gamma_{2,1}$ $C_{3,1}\gamma_{3,1}$ $C_{4,1}\gamma_{4,1}$] > ... < [$C_{1,p}\gamma_{1,p}$ $C_{2,p}\gamma_{2,p}$ $C_{3,p}\gamma_{3,p}$ $C_{4,p}\gamma_{4,p}$] > ... < [$C_{1,m_r}\gamma_{1,m_r}$ $C_{2,m_r}\gamma_{2,m_r}$ $C_{3,m_r}\gamma_{3,m_r}$ $C_{4,m_r}\gamma_{4,m_r}$] >

* < $s_{1,r}$ $s_{2,r}$... $s_{h,r}$... $s_{w,r}$ >

* < $U(s_{1,r})$ $U(s_{2,r})$... $U(s_{h,r})$... $U(s_{w,r})$ >

* ENDU=

...

* $USR_{n+d}=RSDD$ < user free field $n + r$ specifying the last ($r = d$) relative spectral distribution >

* < st_r > ...

* ...

* ENDU=

The parameters are:

RSDW Relative Spectral Distribution – Wavelength.

This acronym means the user free section has the structure for specifying the number and values of wavelengths of the spectral data.

RSDD Relative Spectral Distribution – Data.

This acronym means the user free section has the structure for specifying the relative spectral data.

n number of the first user-defined sections used for spectral data.

d number of the relative spectral distribution that shall be specified.

w number of wavelength.

λ_h value of the h^{th} wavelength, in nm.

st_r numerical code to identify the structure of the user defined section $n + r$. If:

$st_r = 1$ the following relative spectral data are given for a single emission direction;

$st_r = 2$ the following relative spectral data are given for m_r sets of emission directions;

f_r normalizing factor for calculating the r^{th} reduced relative spectral distribution from the r^{th} relative spectral distribution. Dimension 1.

$C_r \gamma_r$ the r^{th} direction of emission of the light identified by plane C_r (azimuthal angle) and the vertical photometric angle γ_r on the systems of planes named C-planes [8] by the CIE. Angles are in degree. Conventionally in [8], the direction $C_r \gamma_r$ is written as $C_r - \gamma_r$ (i.e. 135 - 25 mean the plane $C_r = 135^\circ$ and the vertical photometric angle $\gamma_r = 25^\circ$). To simplify the programme that read the

file the direction is given as a two element vector (i.e. the couple of values 135 25 mean the plane $C_r = 135^\circ$ and the vertical photometric angle $\gamma_r = 25^\circ$). According to the definition of C-planes [8], $0^\circ \leq C_r < 360^\circ$ and with $0^\circ \leq \gamma_r \leq 180^\circ$.

- $s_{h,r}$ value of the r^{th} reduced relative spectral distribution at λ_h . Dimension 1.
- m_r number of set of emission directions for the r^{th} relative spectral distribution.
- $C_{jp} \gamma_{jp}$ is angular direction of the j^{th} vertex of the quadrilateral that identifies the p^{th} set of directions of emission.
- $U(s_{h,r})$ value of the semi-amplitude of the relative spectral distribution tolerance at λ_h multiply by f_r .
Dimension 1.

The maximum number of wavelengths is $w = 471$ ($\lambda_{h+1} - \lambda_h = 1 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_1 = 360 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_w = 830 \text{ nm}$).

The reduced relative spectral distribution $s_{r,h}$ at wavelength λ_h is:

$$s_{r,h} = S_{r,h} f_r \quad (1)$$

where $S_{r,h}$ is the relative spectral distribution at wavelength λ_h .

To obtain the relative spectral distribution $S_{r,h}$ at wavelength λ_h , $s_{r,h}$ shall be divided by f_r . To obtain the tolerance of the relative spectral distribution $U(S_{r,h})$ at wavelength λ_h , $U(s_{r,h})$ shall be divided by f_r .

Due to the length and limitation in the number of lines, it is suggested to give normalized spectral data as integer with 4 digit (5 for the maximum value) and tolerance data as integer with 3 digit. This implicates $f_r = 10000$. Of course the program used to read the file shall consider this data as real numbers.

For all the direction of emission inside the quadrilateral specified with the four vertices $C_j \gamma_j$ ($j = 1, \dots, 4$), see Figure 11, the relative spectral distribution at wavelength λ_i is inside the closed interval $S_{r,h} \pm U(S_{r,h})$.

The program that read the file when finds a USRx code shall test the presence of the RSDW code or of the RSDD code and read the following lines according to the described structure.

Normal programs will read these lines as customers label line.

Figure 11 Graphical draw of the quadrilateral used to specify a set of directions of emission in the CIE C-planes system.

3.3 The CEN file format improvement

As said in §3.1 the original file has many limitations and some improvements are required, if a complete spectral characterization of the luminaire shall be memorized in the file.

The following structure requires the definition of new key lines but give the possibility to specify the measurement uncertainty or tolerance according with measurement results or product specification.

To avoid compatibility problem with the original CEN file new codes for the structured lines that give information on the file format version has been defined. The complete file format specification is show below with reference with the original CEN file [8].

** CENM= 1.0 CEN MODIFIED File Format EMRP-ENG05-SSL1.2.5

* <label line 1>

* ...

* <label line n>

** IDNM=<identification number>

the file continues as the original one. When the key line PHOT= is reached the following two solution are possible:

Solution a)

Solution b)

** PHOT= INCLUDE or <file-spec>

** NSRD = INCLUDE or <file-spec>

see description of the original file

see the following description

** NSRD = INCLUDE or <file-spec>

see the following description

This is a compromise to minimize file changes. Solution a) could be cancelled with a deeper changes of the original file format. The PHOT key line is required by the CEN format protocol but all the information here found are also presented in the NSRD section.

The proposed structure is simple and doesn't consider the possibility to reduce the number of data as done in §3.2. This solution can be criticized because the file could very large, but it is justified by the following considerations:

- Actually manage large file is not a great IT problem.
- The file is used for exchange data, more compact solution (binary file or a more compact structure) can be used for database purpose. These files don't require a standard structure, but they could be optimized according to database requirements.
- The symmetry parameter APOS can be used to reduce the data.
- The tolerance or uncertainty data can be omitted.
- A simple structure simplifies the reader program and reduces the possibilities of errors in writing or reading the file both by software and by humans.

The new key lines are described in the following.

CENM= 1.0 CEN MODIFIED File Format EMRP-ENG05-SSL1.2.5

This is a key line which shall be included in the file. The first line of a file always contains a structured statement indicating that this is a modified CEN file format and including a version number. This is followed

by a reference to this publication that explains the format. The version number is given as a positive real number.

CENR= 1.0 CEN-R MODIFIED File Format EMRP-ENG05-SSL1.2.5

This is a key line which shall be the first line of a CEN radiometric data auxiliary file. It contains a structured statement indicating that this is a modified CEN file format and including a version number. This is followed by a reference to this publication that explains the format. The version number is given as a positive real number.

NSRD = or Normalize Spectral Radiometric Data =

This key lines can substitute the previous used PHOT= key line. In this case the primary purpose of this line is to advise to the application program that the first section of the file containing information, in terms of physical luminaire characteristics, is completed.

If the PHOT= key line is present, then this key lines advises to the application program that a subsection of the file containing information on the spectral properties of the luminaires is starting.

Depending on the location of the spectral data, one of two versions of this line can be used:

NSRD = INCLUDE Used when the radiometric data is part of the CENM= file. The second section of the file immediately follows this line.

NSRD = <file-spec> If any combination of characters other than INCLUDE are used, then this combination of characters is the filename of the separate CENX= file that will be needed by the application program to obtain the radiometric information. The current file ends at this point.

if NSRD = INCLUDE the file continues as follows.

** NSRD = INCLUDE

* <label line 1>

* ...

* <label line n>

** PTYP= C

* APOS= <angle position code>

* TLME= <tilt during measurement>

* ROME= <rotation during measurement>

- * MTLF= <Measured Total Luminous Flux>
- * ULOR= <upward light output ratio>
- * DLOR= <downward light output ratio>
- ** NCON= <g>
- ** NPLA= <c>
- ** NWLH= <w>
- ** < $\lambda_1 \lambda_2 \dots \lambda_h \dots \lambda_w$ >
- ** <DIR 1> <C₁> < γ_1 > <I_{1,1}> <x_{1,1}> <y_{1,1}> <T_{cp,1,1}> <R_{a,1,1}>
- ** <S_{1,1,1} S_{2,1,1} ... S_{h,1,1} ... S_{w,1,1}>
- * <U(S_{1,1,1}) U(S_{2,1,1}) ... U(S_{h,1,1}) ... U(S_{w,1,1})>
- ** <DIR 2> <C₁> < γ_2 > <I_{1,2}> <x_{1,2}> <y_{1,2}> <T_{cp,1,2}> <R_{a,1,2}>
- ** <S_{1,1,2} S_{2,1,2} ... S_{h,1,2} ... S_{w,1,2}>
- * <U(S_{1,1,2}) U(S_{2,1,2}) ... U(S_{h,1,2}) ... U(S_{w,1,2})>
- ** ...
- ** <DIR r> <C_r> < γ_r > <I_{1,r}> <x_{1,r}> <y_{1,r}> <T_{cp,1,r}> <R_{a,1,r}>
- ** <S_{1,l,q} S_{2,l,q} ... S_{h,l,q} ... S_{w,l,q}>
- * <U(S_{1,l,q}) U(S_{2,l,q}) ... U(S_{h,l,q}) ... U(S_{w,l,q})>
- ** ...
- ** <DIR d> <C_c> < γ_g > <I_{c,g}> <x_{c,g}> <y_{c,g}> <T_{cp,c,g}> <R_{a,c,g}>
- ** <S_{c,g,1} S_{c,g,2} ... S_{c,g,h} ... S_{c,g,w}>
- * <U(S_{c,g,1}) U(S_{c,g,2}) ... U(S_{c,g,h}) ... U(S_{c,g,w})>

if NSRD= <file-spec> the separate file containing the radiometric data is as follows:

** CENR= 1.0 CEN-R MODIFIED File Format EMRP-ENG05-SSL1.2.5

And the file continues exactly as shown before.

The meaning of the codes of structured lines remains the same as in the original format. The following new

code is used:

NWLH Number of WaveLengths.

Key line code for specifying the fixed number of wavelength of the relative spectral distribution.

The meaning of the variables are:

g number of vertical photometric angles γ . This number is the same for all the C-planes.

c number of C-planes.

w number of wavelength. The number and values of the wavelength of the relative spectral distribution are the same for all the direction of emission.

d number of the relative spectral distribution that shall be specified. This value is also the number of direction of emission considered: $d = c g$.

DIR r code to specify that the data of the r^{th} ($r = 1, \dots, d$) direction of emission are considered. The main purpose is to facilitate the reading of the file by humans.

λ_h value of the h^{th} wavelength ($h = 1 \dots, w$), in nm.

C_l the l^{th} plane C ($l = 1 \dots, c$) of the CIE C-planes system [8], in degree

γ_q the q^{th} vertical photometric angle γ ($q = 1 \dots, g$) of the CIE C-planes system [8], in degree.

$I_{l,q}$ value of the luminous intensity for the l^{th} plane C and the q^{th} vertical photometric angle γ , in candelas.

$X_{l,q}$ value of the CIE chromaticity coordinate x for the l^{th} plane C and the q^{th} vertical photometric angle γ . Dimension 1.

$Y_{l,q}$ value of the CIE chromaticity coordinate y for the l^{th} plane C and the q^{th} vertical photometric angle γ . Dimension 1.

$T_{cp,l,q}$ value of correlated colour temperature T_{cp} for the l^{th} plane C and the q^{th} vertical photometric angle γ , in kelvin.

$R_{a,l,q}$ value of the CIE 1974 general colour rendering index R_a for the l^{th} plane C and the q^{th} vertical photometric angle γ . Dimension 1.

$U(S_{h,l,q})$ value of the semi-amplitude of the relative spectral distribution tolerance or uncertainty at λ_h for the l^{th} plane C and the q^{th} vertical photometric angle γ . Dimension 1.

The following parameters of the original CEN file are not used:

- LUBA (lumen basis of photometry) because all the luminous intensity data are in candelas
- MULT (MULTIplier) because the data are given as real number in the correct units.

The tolerance parameter $U(S_{i,q,i})$ can be omitted if not relevant. Its meaning can be a real tolerance if the file describe a product characteristics or a measurement uncertainty if the file describe a measurement results.

The use of separate files for radiometric and photometric data should be encouraged because give flexibility to the file use. In this case the first part gives the correct link to the data part or parts that can be modified or managed independently.

The main limitation of this file structure is the fixed number and value of the vertical photometric angles γ for

all the plane C. Generally this could be a problem if the data are obtained using other coordinate systems (like A-plane or B-plane [8] and then converted to the C-plane system. The use of the same wavelength for all the spectral data is not a real limitation because the spectroradiometers work at fixed wavelength. It could become a limit of the file structure in system using two or more detectors, to reduce the measurement time carrying out simultaneous measurements at different directions of emission.

3.4 An XML structure

The actual CEN file has many limitations that were not important when it was designed but that are now important to improve it feasibility. Some points like the possibilities to include more data or file (photographs of the luminaires, mechanical draws, etc.) are welcome by manufactures but not important from the metrological point of view, others (data tolerances, measurement uncertainty, measurement conditions, etc.) shall be included because essential for the correct use of the luminaire in lightning installation design and for the testing lab that shall correctly communicate all the measurement conditions and ancillary parameters.

These improvement can be done following the key code structure of the original format, but the Extensible Markup Language (XML) that defines a set of rules for encoding data in a format that is both human and machine readable gives more flexibilities and delete all the requirements about the number of line and number of charters for line of the “traditional” format. XML files can be read and tested using specific program or routines, but they can be read by all the browsers too. The definition of a standard xml structure for the exchange of luminaires data is out of the scope of this report but a simple structure is here described for the photometric and radiometric parameters described in §3.3.

The most general case is described where:

- the relative spectral density is given at different wavelengths for every measurement directions,
- the steps in the C-Planes or vertical photometric angles are not fixed as well as the number of vertical photometric angles γ .
- all the parameters have the specifications of the uncertainty or tolerance values.

The proposed structure for the luminous intensity distribution is:

```
<Luminous_Intensity_Distribution_Data>
  <!--Luminous Intensity Distribution Data of the light source -->
  <!-- Label:                generic information -->
  <!-- Coordinate_system:    type of the coordinated system used -->
  <!-- Angle_position:       see the APOS key code -->
  <!-- Uncertainty           specification of the uncertainty values. All the following uncertainty or -->
  <!--                       tolerance values are given as: -->
  <!--                        $u_s = 1$ : absolute values -->
  <!--                        $u_s = 2$ : relative values -->
  <!-- Spatial_orientation_v: angles of tilt, rotation and orientation of the light source, in degree -->
```


<!-- Spatial_orientation_u:	uncertainty or tolerance of the angles of tilt, rotation and orientation	-->
<!--	of the light source. For measurement unit see u_s .	-->
<!-- Spatial_orientation_k:	coverage factor of the uncertainty of the angles of tilt, rotation and	-->
<!--	orientation of the light source, dimension 1	-->
<!-- Luminoux_flux_v:	luminous flux of the light source, in lumen	-->
<!-- Luminoux_flux_u:	uncertainty or tolerance of the luminous flux of the light source.	-->
<!--	For measurement unit see u_s .	-->
<!-- Luminoux_flux_k:	coverage factor of the uncertainty of the luminous flux of the light	-->
<!--	source, dimension 1	-->
<!-- Direction	set of data correlated to a given direction of emission	-->
<!-- Direction_c	counter of the directions of emission specified	-->
<!-- Direction_angles_v:	angles (azimuthal and polar) of the given direction, in degree	-->
<!-- Direction_angles_u:	uncertainty or tolerance of the angles (azimuthal and polar) of the	-->
<!--	given direction. For measurement unit see u_s .	-->
<!-- Direction_angles_k:	coverage factors of the angles (azimuthal and polar) of the given	-->
<!--	direction, dimension 1	-->
<!-- Luminous_intensity_v:	luminous intensity emitted in the given direction, in candelas	-->
<!-- Luminous_intensity_u:	uncertainty or tolerance of the luminous intensity emitted in the given	-->
<!--	direction. For measurement unit see u_s .	-->
<!-- Luminous_intensity_k:	coverage factors of the luminous intensity emitted in the given	-->
<!--	direction, dimension 1	-->
<Label	type = "string" > description field	</Label>
<Coordinate_system	type = "string" > C-planes	</Coordinate_system>
<Angle_position	type = "string" > angle position code	</Angle_position>
<Uncertainty	type = "string" > u_s	</Uncertainty>
<Spatial_orientation_v	type = "real" > $\theta \psi \nu$	</Spatial_orientation_v>
<Spatial_orientation_u	type = "real" > $U(\theta) U(\psi) U(\nu)$	</Spatial_orientation_u>
<Spatial_orientation_k	type = "real" > $k(\theta) k(\psi) k(\nu)$	</Spatial_orientation_k>
<Luminoux_flux_v	type = "real" > Φ	</Luminoux_flux_v>
<Luminoux_flux_u	type = "real" > $U(\Phi)$	</Luminoux_flux_u>
<Luminoux_flux_k	type = "real" > $k(\Phi)$	</Luminoux_flux_k>
<Direction	direction_c="1">	
<Direction_angles_v	type = "real" > $C_1 \gamma_1$	</Direction_angles_v>
<Direction_angles_u	type = "real" > $U(C_1) U(\gamma_1)$	</Direction_angles_u>
<Direction_angles_k	type = "real" > $k(C_1) k(\gamma_1)$	</Direction_angles_k>
<Luminous_intensity_v	type = "real" > I_1	</Luminous_intensity_v>
<Luminous_intensity_u	type = "real" > $U(I_1)$	</Luminous_intensity_u>
<Luminous_intensity_k	type = "real" > $k(I_1)$	</Luminous_intensity_k>

```

</Direction>
...
<Direction          direction_c="r">
  <Direction_angles_v  type = "real"  >  $C_r \gamma_r$           </Direction_angles_v>
  <Direction_angles_u  type = "real"  >  $U(C_r) U(\gamma_r)$       </Direction_angles_u>
  <Direction_angles_k  type = "real"  >  $k(C_r) k(\gamma_r)$       </Direction_angles_k>
  <Luminous_intensity_v type = "real"  >  $I_r$                 </Luminous_intensity_v>
  <Luminous_intensity_u type = "real"  >  $U(I_r)$               </Luminous_intensity_u>
  <Luminous_intensity_k type = "real"  >  $k(I_r)$               </Luminous_intensity_k>
</Direction>
...
<Direction          direction_c="d">
  <Direction_angles_v  type = "real"  >  $C_d \gamma_d$           </Direction_angles_v>
  <Direction_angles_u  type = "real"  >  $U(C_d) U(\gamma_d)$       </Direction_angles_u>
  <Direction_angles_k  type = "real"  >  $k(C_d) k(\gamma_d)$       </Direction_angles_k>
  <Luminous_intensity_v type = "real"  >  $I_d$                 </Luminous_intensity_v>
  <Luminous_intensity_u type = "real"  >  $U(I_d)$               </Luminous_intensity_u>
  <Luminous_intensity_k type = "real"  >  $k(I_d)$               </Luminous_intensity_k>
</Direction>
</Luminous_Intensity_Distribution_Data >

```

The proposed structure for the normalize spectral radiometric data is:

```

< Normalize_Spectral_Radiometric_Data>
  <!-- Normalize Spectral Radiometric Data of the light source -->
  <!-- Label:                generic information -->
  <!-- Coordinate_system:    type of the coordinated system used -->
  <!-- Angle_position:       see the APOS key code -->
  <!-- Uncertainty           specification of the uncertainty values. All the following uncertainty or -->
  <!--                       tolerance values are given as: -->
  <!--                        $u_s = 1$ : absolute values -->
  <!--                        $u_s = 2$ : relative values -->
  <!-- Spatial_orientation_v: angles of tilt, rotation and orientation of the light source, in degree -->
  <!-- Spatial_orientation_u: uncertainty or tolerance of the angles of tilt, rotation and orientation -->
  <!--                       of the light source. For measurement unit see  $u_s$ . -->
  <!-- Spatial_orientation_k: coverage factor of the uncertainty of the angles of tilt, rotation and -->
  <!--                       orientation of the light source, dimension 1 -->
  <!-- Luminous_flux_v:      luminous flux of the light source, in lumen -->

```

<!-- Luminous_flux_u:	uncertainty or tolerance of the luminous flux of the light source.	-->
<!--	For measurement unit see u_s .	-->
<!-- Luminous_flux_k:	coverage factor of the uncertainty of the luminous flux of the light	-->
<!--	source, dimension 1	-->
<!-- Direction	set of data correlated to a given direction of emission	-->
<!-- Direction_c	counter of the directions of emission specified	-->
<!-- Direction_angles_v:	angles (azimuthal and polar) of the given direction, in degree	-->
<!-- Direction_angles_u:	uncertainty or tolerance of the angles (azimuthal and polar) of the	-->
<!--	given direction. For measurement unit see u_s .	-->
<!-- Direction_angles_k:	coverage factors of the angles (azimuthal and polar) of the given	-->
<!--	direction, dimension 1	-->
<!-- Luminous_intensity_v:	luminous intensity emitted in the given direction, in candelas	-->
<!-- Luminous_intensity_u:	uncertainty or tolerance of the luminous intensity emitted in the given	-->
<!--	direction. For measurement unit see u_s .	-->
<!-- Luminous_intensity_k:	coverage factors of the luminous intensity emitted in the given	-->
<!--	direction, dimension 1	-->
<!-- Chromaticity_coordinates_v:	chromaticity coordinates x and y of the radiation emitted in the given	-->
<!--	direction, dimension 1	-->
<!-- Chromaticity_coordinates_u:	uncertainty or tolerance of the chromaticity coordinates x and y of the	-->
<!--	radiation emitted in the given direction. For measurement unit see u_s .	-->
<!-- Chromaticity_coordinates_k:	coverage factors of the chromaticity coordinates x and y of the	-->
<!--	radiation emitted in the given direction, dimension 1	-->
<!-- Colour_temperature_v:	correlated colour temperature of the radiation emitted in the given	-->
<!--	direction, in kelvin	-->
<!-- Colour_temperature_u:	uncertainty or tolerance of the correlated colour temperature of the	-->
<!--	radiation emitted in the given direction. For measurement unit see u_s .	-->
<!-- Colour_temperature_k:	coverage factors of the correlated colour temperature of the	-->
<!--	radiation emitted in the given direction, dimension 1	-->
<!-- Colour_rendering_v:	colour rendering indexed of the radiation emitted in the given	-->
<!--	direction, dimension 1	-->
<!-- Colour_rendering_u:	uncertainty or tolerance of the colour rendering indexed of the	-->
<!--	radiation emitted in the given direction. For measurement unit see u_s .	-->
<!-- Colour_rendering_k:	coverage factors of the colour rendering indexed of the	-->
<!--	radiation emitted in the given direction, dimension 1	-->
<!-- Wavelength_v:	wavelength of the relative spectral distribution values, in nanometre	-->
<!-- Wavelength_u:	uncertainty or tolerance of the wavelength of the relative spectral	-->
<!--	distribution values. For measurement unit see u_s .	-->
<!-- Wavelength_k:	coverage factors of the wavelength of the relative spectral	-->
<!--	distribution values, dimension 1	-->


```

<!-- Rel_spectral_distribution_v: relative spectral distribution values, dimension 1 -->
<!-- Rel_spectral_distribution_u: uncertainty or tolerance of the relative spectral distribution values. -->
<!--
                For measurement unit see  $u_s$ . -->
<!-- Rel_spectral_distribution_k: coverage factors of the relative spectral distribution values -->
<!--
                dimension 1 -->
<Label                type = "string" > description field                </Label>
<Coordinate_system    type = "string" > C-planes                </Coordinate_system>
<Angle_position       type = "string" > angle position code    </Angle_position>
<Uncertainty          type = "string" >  $u_s$                 </Uncertainty>
<Spatial_orientation_v type = "real" >  $\theta \psi \nu$                 </Spatial_orientation_v>
<Spatial_orientation_u type = "real" >  $U(\theta) U(\psi) U(\nu)$                 </Spatial_orientation_u>
<Spatial_orientation_k type = "real" >  $k(\theta) k(\psi) k(\nu)$                 </Spatial_orientation_k>
<Luminoux_flux_v      type = "real" >  $\Phi$                 </Luminoux_flux_v>
<Luminoux_flux_u      type = "real" >  $U(\Phi)$                 </Luminoux_flux_u>
<Luminoux_flux_k      type = "real" >  $k(\Phi)$                 </Luminoux_flux_k>
<Direction            direction_c="1">
  <Direction_angles_v type = "real" >  $C_1 \gamma_1$                 </Direction_angles_v>
  <Direction_angles_u type = "real" >  $U(C_1) U(\gamma_1)$                 </Direction_angles_u>
  <Direction_angles_k type = "real" >  $k(C_1) k(\gamma_1)$                 </Direction_angles_k>
  <Luminous_intensity_v type = "real" >  $I_1$                 </Luminous_intensity_v>
  <Luminous_intensity_u type = "real" >  $U(I_1)$                 </Luminous_intensity_u>
  <Luminous_intensity_k type = "real" >  $k(I_1)$                 </Luminous_intensity_k>
  <Chromaticity_coordinates_v type = "real" >  $U(x_1) U(y_1)$                 </Chromaticity_coordinates_v>
  <Chromaticity_coordinates_u type = "real" >  $k(x_1) k(y_1)$                 </Chromaticity_coordinates_u>
  <Colour_temperature_v type = "real" >  $T_{cp,1}$                 </Colour_temperature_v>
  <Colour_temperature_u type = "real" >  $U(T_{cp,1})$                 </Colour_temperature_u>
  <Colour_temperature_k type = "real" >  $k(T_{cp,1})$                 </Colour_temperature_k>
  <Colour_rendering_v type = "real" >  $R_{a,1} R_{1,1} R_{2,1} \dots R_{i,1} \dots R_{e,1}$  </Colour_rendering_v>
  <Colour_rendering_u type = "real" >  $U(R_{a,1})$ 
                                 $U(R_{1,1}) U(R_{2,1})$ 
                                ...
                                 $U(R_{i,1})$ 
                                ...
                                 $U(R_{e,1})$                 </Colour_rendering_u>
  <Colour_rendering_k type = "real" >  $k(R_{a,1})$ 
                                 $k(R_{1,1}) k(R_{2,1})$ 
                                ...
                                 $k(R_{i,1})$ 

```



```

...
    k( $R_{e,1}$ )                                </Colour_rendering_k>
< Wavelength_v          type = "real" >  $\lambda_{1,1} \lambda_{2,1} \dots \lambda_{h,1} \dots \lambda_{w,1}$  </Wavelength_v>
< Wavelength_u          type = "real" >  $U(\lambda_{1,1}) U(\lambda_{2,1})$ 
...
    U( $\lambda_{h,1}$ )
...
    U( $\lambda_{w,1}$ )                                </Wavelength_u>
< Wavelength_k          type = "real" >  $k(\lambda_{1,1}) k(\lambda_{2,1})$ 
...
    k( $\lambda_{h,1}$ )
...
    k( $\lambda_{w,1}$ )                                </Wavelength_k>
<Rel_spectral_distribution_v type = "real" >  $S_{1,1} S_{2,1} \dots S_{i,1} \dots S_{w,1}$  </Rel_spectral_distribution_v>
<Rel_spectral_distribution_u type = "real" >  $U(S_{1,1}) U(S_{2,1})$ 
...
    U( $S_{h,1}$ )
...
    U( $S_{w,1}$ )                                </Rel_spectral_distribution_u>
<Rel_spectral_distribution_u type = "real" >  $k(S_{1,1}) k(S_{2,1})$ 
...
    k( $S_{h,1}$ )
...
    k( $S_{w,1}$ )                                </Rel_spectral_distribution_u>
</Direction>
...
<Direction              direction_c="r">
<Direction_angles_v    type = "real" >  $C_r \gamma_r$  </Direction_angles_v>
<Direction_angles_u    type = "real" >  $U(C_r) U(\gamma_r)$  </Direction_angles_u>
<Direction_angles_k    type = "real" >  $k(C_r) k(\gamma_r)$  </Direction_angles_k>
<Luminous_intensity_v   type = "real" >  $I_r$  </Luminous_intensity_v>
<Luminous_intensity_u   type = "real" >  $U(I_r)$  </Luminous_intensity_u>
<Luminous_intensity_k   type = "real" >  $k(I_r)$  </Luminous_intensity_k>
<Chromaticity_coordinates_v type = "real" >  $U(x_r) U(y_r)$  </Chromaticity_coordinates_v>
<Chromaticity_coordinates_u type = "real" >  $k(x_r) k(y_r)$  </Chromaticity_coordinates_u>
<Colour_temperature_v   type = "real" >  $T_{cp,r}$  </Colour_temperature_v>
<Colour_temperature_u   type = "real" >  $U(T_{cp,r})$  </Colour_temperature_u>
<Colour_temperature_k   type = "real" >  $k(T_{cp,r})$  </Colour_temperature_k>

```



```

<Colour_rendering_v      type = "real" >  $R_{a,r} R_{1,r} R_{2,r} \dots R_{i,r} \dots R_{e,r}$  </Colour_rendering_v>
<Colour_rendering_u      type = "real" >  $U(R_{a,r})$ 
                         $U(R_{1,r}) U(R_{2,r})$ 
                        ...
                         $U(R_{i,r})$ 
                        ...
                         $U(R_{e,r})$  </Colour_rendering_u>
<Colour_rendering_k      type = "real" >  $k(R_{a,r})$ 
                         $k(R_{1,r}) k(R_{2,r})$ 
                        ...
                         $k(R_{i,r})$ 
                        ...
                         $k(R_{e,r})$  </Colour_rendering_k>
< Wavelength_v           type = "real" >  $\lambda_{1,r} \lambda_{2,r} \dots \lambda_{h,r} \dots \lambda_{w,r}$  </Wavelength_v>
< Wavelength_u           type = "real" >  $U(\lambda_{1,r}) U(\lambda_{2,r})$ 
                        ...
                         $U(\lambda_{h,r})$ 
                        ...
                         $U(\lambda_{w,r})$  </Wavelength_u>
< Wavelength_k           type = "real" >  $k(\lambda_{1,r}) k(\lambda_{2,r})$ 
                        ...
                         $k(\lambda_{h,r})$ 
                        ...
                         $k(\lambda_{w,r})$  </Wavelength_k>
<Rel_spectral_distribution_v type = "real" >  $S_{1,r} S_{2,r} \dots S_{i,r} \dots S_{w,r}$  </Rel_spectral_distribution_v>
<Rel_spectral_distribution_u type = "real" >  $U(S_{1,r}) U(S_{2,r})$ 
                        ...
                         $U(S_{h,r})$ 
                        ...
                         $U(S_{w,r})$  </Rel_spectral_distribution_u>
<Rel_spectral_distribution_u type = "real" >  $k(S_{1,r}) k(S_{2,r})$ 
                        ...
                         $k(S_{h,r})$ 
                        ...
                         $k(S_{w,r})$  </Rel_spectral_distribution_u>
</Direction>
...
<Direction               direction_c="d">

```


<Direction_angles_v	type = "real"	> $C_d \gamma_d$	</Direction_angles_v>
<Direction_angles_u	type = "real"	> $U(C_d) U(\gamma_d)$	</Direction_angles_u>
<Direction_angles_k	type = "real"	> $k(C_d) k(\gamma_d)$	</Direction_angles_k>
<Luminous_intensity_v	type = "real"	> I_d	</Luminous_intensity_v>
<Luminous_intensity_u	type = "real"	> $U(I_d)$	</Luminous_intensity_u>
<Luminous_intensity_k	type = "real"	> $k(I_d)$	</Luminous_intensity_k>
<Chromaticity_coordinates_v	type = "real"	> $U(x_d) U(y_d)$	</Chromaticity_coordinates_v>
<Chromaticity_coordinates_u	type = "real"	> $k(x_d) k(y_d)$	</Chromaticity_coordinates_u>
<Colour_temperature_v	type = "real"	> $T_{cp,d}$	</Colour_temperature_v>
<Colour_temperature_u	type = "real"	> $U(T_{cp,d})$	</Colour_temperature_u>
<Colour_temperature_k	type = "real"	> $k(T_{cp,d})$	</Colour_temperature_k>
<Colour_rendering_v	type = "real"	> $R_{a,d} R_{1,d} R_{2,d} \dots R_{i,d} \dots R_{e,d}$	</Colour_rendering_v>
<Colour_rendering_u	type = "real"	> $U(R_{a,d})$ $U(R_{1,d}) U(R_{2,d})$... $U(R_{i,d})$... $U(R_{e,d})$	</Colour_rendering_u>
<Colour_rendering_k	type = "real"	> $k(R_{a,d})$ $k(R_{1,d}) k(R_{2,d})$... $k(R_{i,d})$... $k(R_{e,d})$	</Colour_rendering_k>
< Wavelength_v	type = "real"	> $\lambda_{1,d} \lambda_{2,d} \dots \lambda_{h,d} \dots \lambda_{w,d}$	</Wavelength_v>
< Wavelength_u	type = "real"	> $U(\lambda_{1,d}) U(\lambda_{2,d})$... $U(\lambda_{h,d})$... $U(\lambda_{w,d})$	</Wavelength_u>
< Wavelength_k	type = "real"	> $k(\lambda_{1,d}) k(\lambda_{2,d})$... $k(\lambda_{h,d})$... $k(\lambda_{w,d})$	</Wavelength_k>
<Rel_spectral_distribution_v	type = "real"	> $S_{1,d} S_{2,d} \dots S_{i,d} \dots S_{w,d}$	</Rel_spectral_distribution_v>
<Rel_spectral_distribution_u	type = "real"	> $U(S_{1,d}) U(S_{2,d})$...	

```

                                U(Sh,d)
                                ...
                                U(Sw,d)                                </Rel_spectral_distribution_u>
<Rel_spectral_distribution_u type = "real" > k(S1,d) k(S2,d)
                                ...
                                k(Sh,d)
                                ...
                                k(Sw,d)                                </Rel_spectral_distribution_u>

</Direction>
</Normalize_Spectral_Radiometric_Data>

```

where:

- u_s is a numerical code to specify if the uncertainty or tolerance are given in absolute values ($u_s = 1$) or in relative values ($u_s = 1$).
- θ is the tilt angle of the luminaire, in degrees.
- ψ is the rotation angle of the luminaire, in degrees.
- ν is the orientation angle of the luminaire, in degrees.
- $U(X)$ is the uncertainty or tolerance (according to the data described in the file) of the quantity X . The value specifies the semi-amplitude of the uncertainty or tolerance interval.
- $k(X)$ is coverage factor of the quantity X . Dimension 1.
- Φ is the luminous flux of the luminaire, in lumen.
- $C_r \gamma_r$ is the r^{th} direction of emission of the light identified by plane C_r (azimuthal angle) and the vertical photometric angle γ_r ($r = 1 \dots, d$) of the CIE C-planes system, in degree
- I_r is the value of the luminous intensity emitted in the r^{th} direction of emission, in candelas.
- x_r is the value of the CIE chromaticity coordinate x for the r^{th} direction of emission. Dimension 1.
- y_r is the value of the CIE chromaticity coordinate y for the r^{th} direction of emission. Dimension 1.
- $T_{cp,r}$ is the value of correlated colour temperature T_{cp} for the r^{th} direction of emission, in kelvin.
- $R_{a,r}$ is the value of the CIE 1974 general colour rendering index R_a for the r^{th} direction of emission. Dimension 1.
- $R_{i,r}$ is the value of the i^{th} CIE 1974 special colour rendering index R_i for the r^{th} direction of emission ($i = 1, \dots, e$). Dimension 1.
- $\lambda_{h,r}$ is the value of the h^{th} wavelength ($h = 1 \dots, w$) of the $S_{h,r}$ relative spectral distribution value, in nm.
- $S_{h,r}$ value of the r^{th} relative spectral distribution at wavelength $\lambda_{h,r}$. Dimension 1.

The meaning of the angles θ , ψ and ν is clearly shows in Figure 12.

Figure 12 Axes and angles of orientation of a luminaire in the CIE C-planes system, from [10]. Key: 1 third axis, 2 not relevant, 3 second axis 4 first axis

In the XML terminology, a markup construct that begins with < and ends with > is called tag. A start-tag is for example: <Direction > while an end-tag is for example: </Direction >.

The following conventions can simplify the file according to the users need. Algorithms able to read the XML structure can easily implement them:

- 1) It is possible to use as many tag as one want, only the tag specified in the file structure has a given meaning;
- 2) The same tag can be repeated several times, according to the necessity to specifying data;
- 3) The values given in a tag are valid until a new tag of the same type replace them;
- 4) A tag can be written were it is more useful considering the necessity of compactness and readability of the file:
- 5) The number of values in a tag with variable number of values is not specified.

Convention 1) permits to insert any data in the file structure for flexibility and for specific purpose.

Convention 2) permits to repeat blocks of data in the same file. For example two Normalize_Spectral_Radiometric_Data tags can be written to gives measurement results at two different electrical power conditions or with two different orientation of the luminaire.

Convention 3) permits to delete the repetitions of parameters that remain constant for many data. For example the tag Wavelength_v can be written only once if all the measurements are carried out at the same wavelengths for all the emission directions.

Convention 4) is a consequence of the previously convention. For example the luminaire orientation tag Reference_orientation_v can be written before the Normalize_Spectral_Radiometric_Data tags and the

Luminous_Intensity_Distribution_Data tags if the luminaire orientation is the same for all the data in the file.

The programs able to read XLM file can read all the data given in a tags without knowing their number. This justifies convention 5). At the same time this convention permits great simplification in the file. For example and considering also convention 3), if the uncertainty is equal for all the spectral distribution values only one values of uncertainty can be given in Rel_spectral_distribution_u and Rel_spectral_distribution_k tags.

2. CONCLUSION

The peculiarities of LED sources require the measurement of the relative spectral distribution versus the direction of emission.

This aspect is very important when luminaires are considered. The optical system (lens or reflectors) used to obtain the wanted luminous intensity distribution can create great variations in the radiometric and colorimetric properties of the emitted radiation. In this case the measure of the global value obtainable with an integrating sphere is not sufficient to adequately characterize the luminaire in many applications.

In work of arts lighting often only one luminaire lights the specimen. Spatial variations of the colour of the emitted light can become seriously visible as coloured spots, especially in the uniform background of a picture. This aspect reduces the correct perception of colours and shall be well known when luminaires are selected in the design phase. Generally the use of two or more luminaires to light the same zone reduce the perceived colour variations because the same point receive light from different directions.

In road lighting the mesopic concept can be adopted to reduce the installed power, but maintaining the same safety conditions of the road traffic. In this case the relative spectral distribution is necessary to evaluate the Scotopic-photopic ratio of the emitted radiation and the actual mesopic conditions in applications. If the road is lighted following requirements in luminance, due to the reflection properties of the road surface, generally four or five luminaire are really important to obtain the luminance level in a point on the road surface. The light rays at the highest angle of incidence (respect to the normal of the road surface) give the main contribution, but at these angles the greater variation in the colour properties of luminaires happen. Therefore if the a global radiance distribution is used, the variation in the mesopic real conditions respect to the expected ones obtained with calculations can be significantly high and influence the performance of the installation.

In the road the perceive colour variation is not very important because it can be hided by road irregularities or low luminances. In tunnel lighting the wall are generally white or clear and the differences in colour could become visible and, also if not evaluated by standards requirements, they can create perplexities in the lighting installation performances or, in the most severe situations, they can create distraction to drivers.

The proposed measurement system and the improvement in the CEN file for data exchanges can resolve these problem because give and exhaustive characterization of the luminaires with industrial accuracy without increase the measurement time or cost.

4 REFERENCES

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